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LEVEL OF PERCEPTION OF NATURAL SCIENCE IN A FOREIGN LANGUAGE IN NON-ENGLISH SPEAKING STUDENTS

Kismetova G.,

*Candidate of Pedagogical Sciences, Associate Professor
Makhambet Utemisov West Kazakhstan University*

Zhaskairatova D.

*Master's student of the philological faculty,
Makhambet Utemisov West Kazakhstan University
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Abstract

The article defines interdisciplinary integration and discusses its role in teaching non-English speaking students when learning foreign languages. It also provides various data on recent changes in the pedagogical process of domestic education.

Keywords: interdisciplinary integration, foreign language, education, non-English speaking students.

At the present time in Kazakhstan there is the formation of a new system of education, focused on entering the world space. To achieve this goal, it was necessary to introduce the process of trilingual education, which includes the languages of the trinity (Kazakh, Russian and foreign languages). This process is accompanied by significant changes in the theory and practice of the pedagogical process. Here is some evidence of significant changes over the past six years.

Since 2017, organizations of general secondary education have been teaching individual subjects of the natural and mathematical cycle (NSC) in English. Teaching is carried out taking into account the opinion of parents and students, the willingness of teachers, as well as on the basis of the decision of the Pedagogical Council of the school [7].

Since 2018, for the first time, school leavers have been given the opportunity to take the test in English. In 2021, 351 graduates took Unified national testing (UNT) in English. The average score of graduates taking UNT in English was 84.8 points. In addition, the number of students taking the IELTS and SAT exams increases each year. For example, in the 2020-2021 school year, more than 570 teachers took the certification exams (IELTS), a 39% increase from 2018.

This is a great indicator that today's young people, most of them students and teachers, are aware of and have the opportunity to learn a foreign language so that they can achieve their educational goals from all over the world without any language barriers.

Since 2020, domestic digital multilingual educational platforms such as Bilimland.kz, Kundelik, BilimAI, Daryn online, which have content in English, have started functioning. This is a good opportunity for secondary school students to learn an additional foreign language, which in the future will help them to become a person in their chosen professional field.

In the 2021-2022 school year, there are 3,864 schools teaching subjects in English, including 2,219 rural schools, of which 439 schools are fully immersed and 3,425 are partially immersed. The number of students enrolled natural and mathematical cycle (NSC) subjects in English is 243,324.

Also each year, 1,000 grants are given to universities that train teachers in English language instruction in four specialties of the science and mathematics cycle: «Physics», «Computer Science», «Chemistry», and «Biology».

When comprehending the great truth of nature, students feel the volume of insufficiently systematized knowledge about it. This problem can be solved by integrating subjects. One of the forms of implementation of the integrated approach to learning is the establishment of interdisciplinary links in the lessons of the natural cycle. They play an important role in increasing the practical and scientific-theoretical training of students, the essential feature of which is the mastery of the generalized nature of cognitive activity by schoolchildren. The integrated nature of the acquired knowledge gives the opportunity to apply it in specific situations, when considering private issues, both in the educational and extracurricular activities [5].

Integration is not an end in itself, but a certain system in the teacher's activity; it must solve certain problems of integrated teaching [1]:

- increase the level of knowledge of students in the subject, which is manifested in the depth of the acquired concepts, patterns through their multifaceted interpretation using the information of integrated sciences;
- change the level of intellectual activity by looking at learning material from the perspective of leading ideas, establishing natural correlations between the problems studied;
- Increase the cognitive interest of students, which manifests itself in a desire for active and independent work in class and outside of school hours;
- Include students in creative and research activities.

Interdisciplinary integration plays an important role in teaching foreign language to non-language students. This is due to a number of factors, which were identified in the process of observing the learning process of students of a pedagogical university.

Firstly, non-English speaking students are not always interested in learning a foreign language because

they do not perceive it as a subject contributing to their professional competence. The main source of strengthening the motivational aspect of learning a foreign language at university is the rational use of interdisciplinary integration [9].

Secondly, constant interdisciplinary integration of special subjects and foreign language allows educating students interested in their future professional activity, creative attitude to work, significantly affects the formation of their personality.

Thirdly, interdisciplinary integration allows changing the priority from assimilation of ready-made knowledge to independent active cognitive activity taking into account the need to form an integrated style of thinking in students. An important goal of learning in the conditions of interdisciplinary integration is to achieve not only the results of scientific cognition, but also the very way of obtaining these results, the formation of interdisciplinary structure of knowledge and cognitive independence of the student, the development of creative abilities. Interdisciplinary integration, as an independent stimulus of cognitive interest of students, restructures the learning process: strengthens the generalizing nature of the content of the material studied, the search orientation of the learning activity, its collectivity, mutual assistance of students in its organization; expands business contacts between students and teachers [8].

Thus, using the reliance on interdisciplinary integration, the teacher includes students in active learning and research activities.

In my opinion, interdisciplinary integration is a fundamental methodological principle that contributes to the convergence of different academic disciplines, combines knowledge, skills, and abilities of educational-research activities in different subjects into a coherent system and, thus, resolves the conflict between the subject teaching of a foreign language and formation of teaching and research skills without losing qualitative features of the studied subject.

Also, it should be noted that in English classes you can use linguocountry materials, which should be carefully selected by the teacher. It is the competent selection of linguocountry study materials that is one of the important factors in teaching foreign languages. The solution to this problem largely depends on the teacher, on his ability to effectively implement the selected and developed material in the classroom. Tasks of a linguocountry study nature, which are used in English lessons, should be [6]:

- authentic (representing speech works generated in real communication situations);
- typical (standardized speech works, regularly reproduced in repetitive situations of communication);
- topical (reflecting the current stage of socio-verbal interaction of communicants).

It is very important to understand that mastering the culture of the country of the target language is based on the principles of authentic communication, interactivity, and learning the language in a cultural context [3].

The system of multilingualism among the subjects of natural and mathematical direction determines the relevance of the problem of integration in education, which provides for the creation of fundamentally new educational information with appropriate content of educational material, educational and methodological support, new technologies.

Finally, it encourages students to redefine their need and ability to communicate in three languages.

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